

Equal-Life Second wave scientific papers

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects

Project Number: 874724

Project Acronym: Equal-Life

Work package 10 - Deliverable D10.10

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.1	01/11/2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial version
1.2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amended following comments by PI's
1.3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final version

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Table of Contents

1	Summary	4
2	Published papers.....	4
3	Papers in final stages of preparation	5
4	Popular	6

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1 Summary

This report gives an overview of the published scientific papers were published between January 1st 2022 and December 31st 2022 in the context of the Equal-Life project (*Chapter 2*) and a list of papers per work package (WP) that are in the final stages of preparation in December 2022, to be submitted early 2022 or under review (*Chapter 3*) and a list of publications aimed at the general public (*Chapter 4*). For the Equal-Life publication policy, we refer to D10.2.

2 Published papers

The following scientific papers were published between January 1st 2022 and December 31st 2022 in the context of the Equal-Life project:

- Whipp A.M., M Heinonen-Guzejev, KH Pietiläinen, I van Kamp, J Kaprio, Whipp et al: “Branched chain amino acids linked to depression in young adults“ *Frontiers in Neuroscience* (2022).
- Wang Z, Whipp AM, Heinonen-Guzejev M, Kaprio J. Age at separation, residential mobility, and depressive symptoms among twins in late adolescence and young adulthood: a FinnTwin12 cohort study. *medRxiv*. 2022 Jan 1
- Wang Z, Whipp A, Heinonen-Guzejev M, Kaprio J. Age at Separation of Twin Pairs in the FinnTwin12 Study. *Twin Research and Human Genetics*. 2022 May 23:1-7.
- van Kamp, Irene, Kerstin Persson Waye, Katja Kanninen, John Gulliver, Alessandro Bozzon, Achilleas Psyllidis, Hendriek Boshuizen et al. "Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project." *Environmental Epidemiology* 6, no. 1 (2022): e183. doi: 10.1097/EE9.000000000000183.
- Vasileios Miliias, Achilleas Psyllidis. “Measuring spatial age segregation through the lens of co-accessibility to urban activities”. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2022.101829>
- Dzhambov, Angel M., et al. Home gardens and distances to nature associated with behavior problems in alpine schoolchildren: Role of secondhand smoke exposure and biomarkers. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 2022, 243: 113975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.113975>
- Michail Evangelos Terzakis, Maud Dohmen, Irene van Kamp, Maarten Hornikx “Noise indicators relating to non-auditory health effects in children - A systematic literature review” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192315633>
- Loh, K., Fintor, E., Nolden, S., & Fels, J. (2022). Children’s intentional switching of auditory selective attention in spatial and noisy acoustic environments in comparison to adults. *Developmental Psychology*, 58(1), 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001239>
- Loh Karin, Yadav Manuj, Persson Waye Kerstin, Klatte Maria, Fels Janina (2022). Toward Child-Appropriate Acoustic Measurement Methods in Primary Schools and Daycare Centers . *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2022.688847>

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- Roos Teeuwen, Achilleas Psyllidis, Alessandro Bozzon "Measuring children's and adolescents' accessibility to greenspaces from different locations and commuting settings" Received 13 May 2022; Received in revised form 23 September 2022; Accepted 3 November 2022
Computers, Environment and Urban Systems

These papers are also added to the continuous reporting module in the EC portal.

3 Papers in final stages of preparation

The following papers are in the final stages of preparation in December 2022 and will be submitted early 2023 or are currently under review.

WP1

- Dzambov et al., Protective effect of restorative possibilities on cognitive function and mental health in children and adolescents: a scoping review including the potential role of physical activity. Special Issue Environmental Research, *submitted*
- Schreckenberget al., Scoping review on stress as a potential mediator in the association between exposome, mental health and cognition in children and adolescents. Special Issue Environmental Research, *in preparation*
- Natalia Vincens et al., A scoping review on how developmental perspectives have been incorporated in the research about exposome and mental health in children and adolescents. Special Issue Environmental Research, *in preparation*
- Maria Klatte et al., Coping and self-regulation as potential buffers in the impact of exposome on mental health and cognitive development of children and adolescents: a scoping review. Special Issue Environmental Research, *in preparation*
- Kerstin Persson Waye et al., Sleep as a mediator in the association between exposome and children's and adolescents' mental health: a scoping review. Special Issue Environmental Research, *in preparation*
- Kerstin Persson Way et al., An exposome perspective on mental health and cognitive development of children and adolescents: a conceptual paper in a life-course perspective. Special Issue Environmental Research, *in preparation*

WP2:

- Arto Alatalo, Izaque de Sousa Maciel, Nina Kucharikova, Sweelin Chew, Irene van Kamp, Maria Foraster, Jordi Julvez, Katja M Kanninen. The interaction between circulating cell-free mitochondrial DNA and inflammatory cytokines in predicting substantial mental health disorder risk in adolescents: an explorative study. *In preparation*
- Izaque de Sousa Maciel, Katja Kanninen et al, Protein-based biomarkers for mental health. *In preparation*
- Marja Heinonen-Guzejev, Alyce Whipp, Teemu Palviainen, Wang Zhiyang, Anu Ranjit, Irene van Kamp, Jaakko Kaprio, Occupational noise exposure and depression in young Finnish adults. *IJERPH, in preparation*

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WP4:

- Gudi-Mindermann, H., White, M. Roczen, J., Dreger, S. Riedel, N., & Bolte, G. Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: A new conceptual framework of the Social Exposome. Special Issue Environmental Research, *under review*
- Maud Dohmen et al., Systematic review effects on noise on cognition and motivation. *In preparation*.

WP5:

- Roos Teeuwen, Achilleas Psyllidis. Easy as child's play? Co-designing a network-based metric for children's access to play space" Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM). *In preparation*.

4 Popular Publications

Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children. Irene van Kamp and team (openaccessgovernment.org) - June 2022 <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/>

Irene van Kamp and Equal-Life team: Interviews Improving child exposome and quality of life (openaccessgovernment.org) October 2022

<https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/article/equal-life-team-improving-child-exposome-and-quality-of-life/145820/>

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